

High Speed, Single Cycle Resolution Reliability System for RF-MEMS Switches

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Abstract – This paper presents a novel platform for high speed, single cycle resolution lifetime testing of RF-MEMS switches and the results collected. The platform utilizes an FPGA based monitoring system to allow switch cycling up to 45 kHz. In addition, multiple real-time resistance measurements are made each cycle, allowing the accurate detection of intermittent failures. Each measurement is then analyzed and all failures, as well as a periodic sample of passing cycles, are stored and transferred to an external PC for further analysis. Results presented here verify the platform’s functionality. Moreover, the results indicate that brief intermittent failures can occur hundreds of millions of cycles before end of life failure, which illustrates the need for single cycle resolution when qualifying RF-MEMS switches for use in larger RF systems.

To the authors’ knowledge, this is the first reported reliability system capable of single cycle resolution at high cycling frequencies.

Index Terms – Radiofrequency microelectromechanical systems, reliability, life testing

I. INTRODUCTION

Microelectromechanical system (MEMS) switches for RF applications have been in development for the past two decades. The ability to have a low insertion loss, high isolation RF switch on the micron scale is very appealing, especially in areas where power consumption and linearity dominate the system design specifications. To date, many groups have demonstrated RF-MEMS switches and several have produced switches that operate for over 1 billion cycles. Reliability and repeatability are an active area of interest [1] and additional improvements to testing capabilities would facilitate wide scale adoption of the technology.

MEMS devices present a unique challenge for characterization due to high bias voltage requirements, unique biasing waveforms, switch bounce, electrical arcing, contact evolution among others. Currently available commercial equipment is incapable of single cycle resolution monitoring at reasonable switching speeds. To date, several test setups have been reported that have worked around some of these challenges to obtain useful device characteristics. In [2], the authors presented a RF-MEMS contact switch test setup that operated at a 20 kHz cycling rate. An RF input to the switch and a crystal detector on the output were used to monitor the contact characteristics and this data was periodically sampled. In [3], a similar system was used, but this time capacitive switches were tested with a 60 kHz cycling frequency. More recently, [4] addressed the issue of cycle resolution with an

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the MEMS lifetime test platform.

integrated CMOS sensor that produces a PWM waveform based on the capacitance of the switch. This sensor functions without impacting the operation of the switch and provides a high resolution set of data. It is intended as an on-chip built-in self test. For reliability characterization bias waveform shaping and data transfer provisions may be required.

Fig. 2. Finite state machine used to control the HDL defined reliability module.

Fig. 3. Typical response of the reliability system. Trace C4 in green is the bias waveform produced by the FPGA board and trace C2 in pink is amplified crystal diode detector output. Markers indicate the readout points.

This paper presents a novel MEMS, high resolution, high speed lifetime test platform and the data collected. The system utilizes an FPGA based monitoring system to perform real-time contact resistance measurements, synchronized to a switch's current state. This occurs twice per cycle at a cycling rate up to 45 kHz. The data is evaluated within the FPGA and only key points are retained. This allows a very accurate history of the contact resistance evolution without sacrificing testing speed.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

It is desirable to have a MEMS switch lifetime testing platform that can accurately control the state of the device under test (DUT) at high speeds, monitor and assess the contact resistance in real-time, recreate real-world operating conditions and be able to evaluate multiple devices in parallel.

In an attempt to meet the above criteria, the system shown in Fig. 1 was developed. This system utilizes a custom FPGA board, DC bias amplifier, RF generator, negative crystal diode detector and an inverting amplifier for the detected signal. An RF based test was chosen to allow testing of both contact-based and capacitive RF-MEMS switches.

The custom FPGA board incorporates Xilinx's Spartan 3a FPGA chip, an analog-to-digital converter (ADC), digital-to-analog converter (DAC), external DDR memory and Ethernet communication hardware. One of the amplifiers external to the FPGA board amplifies the DAC to provide the high-voltage bias required by some electrostatic RF-MEMS switches and buffer the FPGA board from the DC bias. The inverting amplifier driving the ADC adjusts the detector's output voltage to maximize the ADC's resolution in addition to providing addition protection for the FPGA board.

The resources on the FPGA chip were partitioned for two tasks, reliability testing and data retrieval. The reliability testing module was responsible for controlling the state of the DUT (i.e. open or closed) via the DAC, monitoring the contact resistance and determining if any failures occurred. The master finite state machine (FSM) that drove this module is shown in Fig. 2. As shown, two data points are collected every cycle, one in the open state and one in the closed state. This

Fig. 4. Calibration results for the test system and the associated equation used to convert ADC measured voltages into contact resistances. Insert shows the fixture used for the calibration standards and RF-MEMS switches.

allows the system to detect both stuck closed and high resistance failures as well as variations in the two states throughout the lifetime of the device. More read points can be included if needed.

As the reliability module was required to perform multiple tasks in parallel and it was imperative that it operate in real-time to avoid missing cycle data, it was implemented using the FPGA hardware. This allowed each task to operate independently, with its own set of hardware, while still remaining synchronized via the master FSM. In addition, Verilog provides the capability to duplicate this module during design synthesis, automatically adjusting data port addresses, which simplifies the task of expanding the system to test more devices. Hence, parallelizing the system to multiple device tests is straightforward. In addition, since each module is assigned a unique set of hardware, there is no performance penalty.

Each resistance measurement is evaluated to be a success or failure based on the acceptable limits for a given device. The results are analyzed in real-time and a majority of the success data points are discarded. A reduced sample set of the success points is preserved to monitor parametric failure of the device. This is done using an adaptive logarithmic algorithm. When the test begins, the system will store data nearly every cycle. As time progresses the frequency of storage decreases until it reaches a predefined minimum rate. If a failure occurs, the frequency of successful samples stored reverts to its initial high storage rate to capture potentially important contact behavior after the failed cycle. All failures have the cycle number and the ADC value for the on-state and off-state permanently stored for transfer to the user.

The other partition of the FPGA chip, data retrieval, was implemented using the Xilinx Microblaze soft-core

microcontroller. Periodically, the data retrieval module would poll the reliability module to see if any new data has been collected. When new data was present, it was retrieved and stored within the external DDR memory until the user requested it. Since the soft-core microcontroller was directly programmable in C/C++, it provided the most straightforward way to implement this module. In addition, this approach simplified the utilization of different communication protocols.

External to the FPGA chip were the DAC and ADC chips. The DAC, which produced the bias for the MEMS switch, was an 8-bit chip capable of 25 mV resolution with a rise time from 0 V to VDD of 1.7 μ s. These performance characteristics provided sufficient control over the output waveform to allow bounce mitigating shaping of the bias signal as shown in Fig. 3. Switch bounce has been shown to play a major role in accelerating the degradation of MEMS switches and controlling it is necessary for lifetime test systems [5].

The ADC, with an accuracy of +/- 0.2 mV, was used to read the amplified voltage from the RF detector. This device operated by first triggering a sample and then serially reading the data from that sampled voltage. While the actual sampling took place in under 50 ns, the reading process took just under 8 μ s. This chip became the limiting cycling speed factor for the system, putting the maximum operating frequency at approximately 45 kHz.

To calibrate the platform, a set of seven standards were created; each consists of a resistor in series with a 50 Ω transmission line. A calibration is valid for a given frequency and power level. Each of the seven standards was measured and the ADC readings recorded. Fig. 3 shows the calibration plot obtained for a 1 GHz, -10 dBm RF input.

III. SYSTEM RESULTS

To verify the validity of the system and obtain the initial data sets, several tests were performed on an electrostatic RF-MEMS switch. Each switch was placed in the microwave fixture shown in the insert of Fig. 4. All of the tests reported here are done with a continuous RF signal applied to the device. The switch was operated at 45 kHz with the waveform shown in Fig. 3 and 1 GHz, -10 dBm RF input signal. It is expected that switch resistance will decrease to a stable value during the initial cycling [6]. A measured example of this behavior is shown in Fig. 5, where the switch has an initial contact resistance of approximately 6 Ω and decreases to 5.5 Ω over the first 44 million cycles.

The next switch tested was allowed to run for 900 million cycles before the test was halted. The results, shown in Fig. 6, highlight several key traits of the switch as well as the accuracy of the system. First, the initial contact resistance starts at 7.67 Ω and improves to under 7 Ω over the first 10 million cycles. Secondly, there is an initial intermittent failure that occurs at cycle 624,575,512. This is the type of failure

Fig. 5. Initial contact resistance evolution. Measured data points are shown as blue circles. A moving average of the data is plotted with a solid black line. Dashed black lines show $\pm 3\sigma$.

Fig. 6. Lifetime data collected at 45 kHz from an RF-MEMS switch showing initial contact resistance improves over the first 10 million cycles and an initial intermittent failure on cycle 624,575,512.

that would likely be missed in periodic sampling systems or take a very long time to reach in high resolution, slow cycling test.

A second test was performed, for approximately 1 billion cycles, with a non-optimum waveform, which introduced a visible bounce during switch closure. This waveform was chosen to highlight switch failure patterns. The results of the test are shown in Fig. 7 with a magnified view of the early failures shown in Fig. 8. The failures, which initially appeared bunched together, are actually spread out over the course of 1 million cycles. As pointed out previously, these early failures would most likely be missed in systems that periodically samples data. Such intermittent failures, while brief and infrequent initially, can have a catastrophic impact on certain RF systems. For instance, a failed RF switch in a transmit/receive module could directly connect the transmit chain's power amplifier to the receive chain's low noise amplifier (LNA), most likely destroying the LNA.

Fig. 7. Lifetime data collected with a non-optimum waveform showing impact of the bias waveform on switch performance.

Fig. 8. Magnified view of the early failures during the non-optimum waveform test, emphasizing the separation and infrequency of each failure.

Another important characteristic captured in Fig. 7 is the increase in frequency of intermittent failures as the device accumulates cycles. This increased frequency was a characteristic of all devices tested and could be used as a prognostic tool to evaluate the health of an RF-MEMS switch.

Having the ability to test RF-MEMS switches with single cycle resolution at high cycling speeds gives detailed insight into switch behavior not previously captured and can be used as a tool for technology development and qualification.

IV. CONCLUSION

A high speed, single cycle resolution reliability system for RF-MEMS switches was reported. The platform has the capability of cycling devices at up to 45 kHz with an arbitrarily defined bias waveform. It offers the unique capability for reliability systems by performing high cycling speed tests with single cycle resolution. This allows

intermittent failures that occur for only one cycle to be captured and recorded. In addition, a hardware based adaptive storage system provides a compact and meaningful set of data to study contact behavior.

Flexibility in the employed hardware and software solutions allows the system to be easily parallelized and to utilize multiple data transfer protocols. In addition, the sampling frequency can be adjusted to capture multiple points per waveform if desired.

This system provides a useful tool for studying the behavior of RF-MEMS switches under a variety of operating conditions. Current plans include investigating the impact of the RF power level, temperature of the operating environment and cold-switching versus hot-switching lifetime comparisons. In addition, various switch parameters, such as contact metallurgy, actuator geometry, gaseous ambient, actuation waveforms, etc., can be optimized to improve the reliable operation of the RF-MEMS switch devices.

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